

PREGNANCY & COVID-19

Testing & Vaccinations

CAN I GET TESTED FOR COVID-19 IF I AM PREGNANT?

Yes! The results of a COVID-19 test can help pregnant people and their doctors make informed decisions about ongoing care. Testing can also help limit the spread of COVID-19 to others in case of a positive result. COVID-19 testing is safe and free to anyone in the U.S.

Vaccination is the best way to reduce the risks of COVID-19 infection for pregnant people or recently pregnant people according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).

Here are a few facts about COVID-19 testing and vaccination during pregnancy.

HOW TO PROTECT YOURSELF AGAINST COVID-19 IF YOU ARE PREGNANT

Pregnant people should take the same precautions as non-pregnant people. In addition to getting vaccinated, pregnant people should continue to practice social distancing, wear a mask, and wash their hands often. Common symptoms of COVID-19 infection include a fever, cough, difficulty breathing, and loss of smell and taste. Call your local health center if you have any of these symptoms. Follow your health care providers directions and testing instructions.

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ARE COVID-19 VACCINES SAFE TO GET WHILE PREGNANT?

Yes! The CDC recommends COVID-19 vaccines for all eligible people age 5 years and older. This includes those who are pregnant, breastfeeding, or plan to become pregnant. All of the current COVID-19 vaccines can be given to pregnant people. Pregnant people can get the vaccine in any trimester. None of the COVID-19 vaccines contain the live virus that causes COVID-19 so a COVID-19 vaccine cannot make anyone sick with COVID-19, including pregnant people or their babies. Also, there is no evidence that COVID-19 vaccines cause fertility problems.

WHY SHOULD I GET THE COVID-19 VACCINE?

- Getting a COVID-19 vaccine can protect you from severe illness from COVID-19.
- Pregnant people who test positive for COVID-19 while pregnant are at higher risk of severe illness compared to non-pregnant people. They are also at higher risk of poor pregnancy outcomes.
- Pregnant people with **underlying conditions** like obesity, hypertension, or diabetes may be at **higher risk** of complications from COVID-19.
- COVID-19 vaccines do not have the live virus that can infect or make someone sick with COVID-19, not even in pregnant people or their babies.
- Growing evidence shows the vaccine can **build antibodies** that might protect the fetus or baby, both during pregnancy and while breast-feeding.
- COVID-19 vaccine clinical trials have gone through the same **high standards** and requirements as other vaccines. Research using mRNA has been going on for many years, which is how the vaccines were able to be developed quickly. COVID-19 vaccines were developed using the same safety standards required for all vaccines. The CDC and FDA continue to provide updated safety information to the public.
- The vaccine is **free of charge** regardless of immigration status or proof of insurance.

If you have more questions about the COVID-19 vaccines or testing, talk with your healthcare provider about any possible risks or concerns.

For more information, see “COVID-19 Vaccines While Pregnant or Breastfeeding” on the CDC website.
<https://bit.ly/3AW02OW>